

CAUSES OF ANXIETY IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Annotation: The three-part article sheds light on school and background causes of helping situations that appear in preschool children.

Key words: children of preschool age, anxiety, fear, anxious state, dissatisfaction.

The scientific and theoretical study of the psychological characteristics of preschool children is of great practical importance in higher pedagogical education.

That is why psychological changes in preschool children are one of the important factors affecting the development of society. When a child reaches school age, serious changes occur in his mental development. The reason is that it is from this period that the child's independent activity expands. At the same time, alarming situations in them also begin to appear.

In preschool children, the occurrence of problems related to adaptation to the environment, the inability to accept news and changes at once, and being away from parents for a long time can cause anxiety. Children are sensitive creatures by nature. During this period, the kindergarten environment plays an important role in their lives. Discipline in the kindergarten, a large number of people, the level of noise, and many aspects of the unfamiliar environment can cause fear, anxiety, and worry in some children. In addition, the family environment, problems in the relationship between parents also serve as a factor that causes the child to worry and worry.

Even if education is based on excessive demands, the child cannot cope with difficulties. As a result, the fear of doing something wrong increases. Such children often make a lot of mistakes, and the feeling of fear of reprimand and punishment increases, which creates anxiety in them.

In general, anxiety and worry are one of the most common and observed conditions in children of this age. If the anxiety is temporary, the child will adapt to the environment after a certain time. He can overcome his fear and anxiety. But if the anxiety state is very strong, such children cannot adapt to the environment, they may lag behind other children in rapid development. In the future, this situation can have a negative impact on the child's place in life.

Anxious children are distinguished from other children by frequent manifestations of anxiety and worry, as well as a large number of fears. Such children are very sensitive and impressionable. They may worry about trivial things. Such children often have a low self-esteem, so they stand out from others by their passive actions. Anxious children are very sensitive to their failures, react harshly to them. They refuse any activity that they experience difficulties. For example, painting, memorizing poetry, dancing, etc.

According to E. Savina, the most important causes of childhood anxiety are improper upbringing of the child and unfavorable relations between parents, especially the mother. Thus, the rejection of the child by the mother causes him anxiety because of the inability to satisfy the need for love, affection and protection. In this case, fear arises: the child feels the conditionality of material love ("If I do bad things, they won't love me"). A child's dissatisfaction with his need for love prompts him to seek to satisfy it. Children's anxiety can also be the result of a symbiotic relationship between the child and the mother, when the mother feels that she is one with her child and tries to protect him from the difficulties and challenges of life. He "attaches" to himself, protects against imaginary, non-existent dangers. As a result, when a child is left without a mother, he becomes anxious, easily lost, anxious and afraid. Instead of activity and independence, passivity and dependence develop.

Another situation that causes anxiety in children is competition. Competition is a particularly strong concern in children raised in this hypersocialized environment. In this case, children become competitive and strive to be the first to achieve the highest results in any case. In addition, the situation of increased responsibility also creates anxiety in children. When an anxious child finds himself in this situation, his anxiety is manifested in connection with the fear of not living up to the expectations of adults and rejection by him.

Summary: Thus, the cause of anxiety is always the child's internal conflicts, his disagreement with himself, the inconsistency of his aspirations, and when one of his strong desires conflicts with another, one need interferes with another. The most common reasons for such an internal conflict are as follows: a quarrel between the child's peers and when he is forced to take the side of one of them over the other in this situation; incompatibility of different systems of requirements for the child; the contradictions between the inflated claims inspired by the parents and the real possibilities of the child, on the other hand,

are manifested in the dissatisfaction of basic needs, such as the need for love and independence.

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